

Determination of Stability Constants of N-[5-Methylsalicylidene]-Benzylamine Complexes with Y^{3+} , La^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+}

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Potentiometric studies have been carried out on metal complexes of Y^{3+} , La^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+} with N-[5-methylsalicylidene]-benzylamine. The proton association constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at ionic strength 0.1 M in 75:25 percent (v/v) dioxan-water medium. The order of stability constants of the chelates is found to be $Dy^{3+} > Sm^{3+} > Gd^{3+} > Y^{3+} > Nd^{3+} > Pr^{3+} > La^{3+}$.

IN the present communication, the successive stability constants of the complexes of N-[5-methylsalicylidene]-benzylamine with various trivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

The Corning Model 12, a precision research pH meter with a combined glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for measuring 'B' values (pH meter readings) of the solutions. The changes in 'B' can be measured with an accuracy of 0.005 unit.

Experimental

The ligand N-[5-methylsalicylidene]-benzylamine was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 5-methyl-salicylaldehyde and benzylamine in methanol. The product was repeatedly crystallised to get a pure compound (observed m. p. 64°).

Dioxan used was purified by usual method reported in literature². The medium of titration was 75:25 percent (v/v) dioxan-water mixture. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength. The titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere.

The metal perchlorates were prepared from the metal carbonates of A. R. grade using perchloric acid of A. R. grade. All these were standardised complexometrically³ by edta titrations. All the measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The experimental details and computational methods are the same as described in an earlier communication⁴. Experimental method of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL . The titrations were performed in duplicate to test the reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

It may be stated here that the reagent does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions

described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the titration and by the absence of any significant drift in pH meter readings even after one hour.

In the ligand it is the phenolic (OH) group which takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y', the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

The curve between 'B' and the corresponding \bar{n}_A value was plotted to get the formation curve (Fig. 1). The formation curve extends over a range of $0.779 < \bar{n}_A < 1.585$ and is wave-like. From this curve pK_2^H which corresponds to the association of proton to imino-nitrogen was evaluated at $\bar{n}_A = 1.5$. The pK_1^H which corresponds to the association of proton to phenoxide ion of the reagent and pK_2^H were also determined by least square method.

Fig. 1. Formation curve of N-[5-methylsalicylidene] Benzylamine.

\bar{n} and pL values were calculated and \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the

formation curves of the metal complex-ion equilibria (Fig. 2). From the formation curves, the values of stability constants $\log K_1$ were evaluated which corresponded to 1:1 complexes at $\bar{n}=0.5$. These were further corroborated by plotting $\log\left[\frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}}\right]$ vs pL (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Metal-Ligand systems of N-[5-methylsalicylidene] benzylamine.

Fig. 3. N-[5-Methylsalicylidene] benzylamine.

The complexation reaction is represented below :

LM corresponds to the species

The $\log K_2$ for these metal ions could not be evaluated due to precipitation probably due to metal ion hydrolysis. The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability of trivalent metal-chelates was found to be

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

t=25°		$\mu=0.1M$						
Cations	H ⁺	Y ³⁺	La ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺
$\log K_1$	11.54	10.85	7.80	9.05	9.25	11.15	11.02	11.67
$\log K_2$	8.09	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

*For proton association (H⁺), K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species LH and LH⁺ respectively, while for metal ions K_1 correspond to the species ML₁.

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